

Co-creating Computer Supported Collective Intelligence in Citizen Science Hubs

Aelita Skarzauskiene¹[0000-0003-1606-0676] and Monika Mačiulienė²[0000-0002-8527-7468]

¹ Vilnius Gediminas Technical University, Vilnius, Lithuania

² Vilnius Gediminas Technical University, Vilnius, Lithuania

aelita.skarzauskiene@vilniustech.lt

Abstract. Collective Intelligence system can be conceptualized as knowledge network created by web-mediated interaction amongst individuals with personal knowledge. Citizen Science Hubs are ideal environment for collective intelligence to emerge and can be considered as Collective Intelligence systems. Citizen Science aims to bring different stakeholders together and bridge society with science in an institutionalized way by developing Collective Intelligence ecosystem which entails collaboration between all QH stakeholders: the public and researchers/institutes, also governments and funding agencies. The development of crowdsourcing platforms and networks that enable volunteers to contribute to different research projects, the use of machine learning technologies and artificial intelligence may extend ecosystem capabilities, especially those depending on human intelligence. It is essential that Citizen Science platforms leverage the complementary strengths of humans and machines to take full advantage of the onslaught of data being experienced across the disciplines. With the aim to deeper understand complexity of relationships at different levels of human-computer interaction in Collective Intelligence ecosystem, conceptual model was developed on the basis of theoretical insights. The framework presented in Figure 1 below provides a holistic view into the Citizen Science Hub as co-creative collective intelligence ecosystem.

Keywords: Collective Intelligence, Co-creation, Citizen Science.

1 Introduction

1.1 ICT supported Collective Intelligence Systems

All the types of human groups can be regarded as a source of collective intelligence. Community, according Luo et al. [1] “refers to any human group in which the members have some common characteristics, share same interests or views, have similar purposes.” Lykourantzou et al. [2] define online community as a “system which hosts an

adequately large group of people, who act for their individual goals, but whose group actions aim and may result – through technology facilitation – in a higher-level intelligence and benefit of the community.” There is no doubt that the widespread and availability of the Internet is one of the prerequisites for a new form of interconnection, different forms of social cohesion and conditions to collectively build community interactions. Enabled by the information communication technologies (ICT) and under the right circumstances “the communities may exhibit higher intelligent features than a traditional community does because artificial intelligence provides an effective communication channel for massive exchange of data, information and knowledge” [3]. The computation capabilities of the modern ICT also may be of great help for the information processing tasks within the entire community. Similar as in the case of “swarm intelligence” [4] in natural systems, Collective Intelligence systems consist of human beings and supporting computer systems. Human intelligence blended together with intelligent machines enable communities to resolve problems and achieve unprecedented results.

To make use of collective intelligence potential, a number of leading Research Performing and Funding Organisations (RPFOS) worldwide have established transdisciplinary hubs for stimulating and supporting excellent citizen science. These Citizen Science Hubs are ideal environment for collective intelligence to emerge and can be considered as CI systems. Citizen Science (CS) projects involve members of the general public and other QH stakeholders as active participants in research. **Citizen science projects** may cover various scientific fields, such as biology, astronomy, medicine, computer science, statistics, psychology and engineering. Scientists usually create citizen-science programs to capture crowdsourced data that would be hard to obtain otherwise due to time, geographic, or resource constraints, or to make use of the collective intelligence of humans that outperform automatic procedures in identifying and classifying information in data collected via various ways. Classical examples are the identification of protein or galaxy structures in massively collected relevant images.

This paper presents conceptual model of Collective intelligence ecosystem focusing on human-computer interaction to serve the needs of the QH stakeholders. The research provides insights about the collaboration specificities and operating models at Micro, Meso and Macro levels supporting Citizen Science communities to deliver intended intellectual outcomes, therefore leading to inclusive and more effective science.

1.2 Citizen Science Hub as Collective Intelligence ecosystem

Collective Intelligence system can be conceptualized as knowledge network created by web-mediated interaction amongst individuals with personal knowledge. Citizen Science Hubs aim to bring different stakeholders together and bridge society with science in an institutionalized way by developing Collective Intelligence ecosystem which entails collaboration between all QH stakeholders: the public and researchers/institutes, also governments and funding agencies [5]. New knowledge, new ideas, found solutions, suggested problem solving methods, shaped up public opinion, structured opinions and views, developed innovations, prototypes, generated added value, etc. are considered to be intellectual capacities of the ecosystem. The development of crowdsourcing

platforms and networks that enable volunteers to contribute to different research projects, the use of machine learning technologies and artificial intelligence may extend ecosystem capabilities, especially those depending on human intelligence. The Structural Model of Community Intelligence [1] explains how the community level intelligence may generate from the knowledge-related activities of the participants or the community members. Firstly, the community should “contain a memory system that stores information and knowledge, analogous to the memory system in a human brain. Secondly, the community should have the capability of ‘intelligent’ problem-solving, i.e. the capability of utilizing the stored knowledge to solve problems. Theoretical insights and empirical research results [6] reveal that at the current knowledge level the quality of human-computer interaction influences in the CI the performance of the system as a whole. The knowledge network embodies the collective knowledge of the community and consist of a technological network or media network that supports information and knowledge transfer, a human network of community members, and a content network of knowledge and information, which is hosted in humans and computer systems [1]. Human intelligence in convergence with “machine” intelligence create opportunities for network participants to achieve impressive activity results. A range of digital infrastructures (e.g. mobile apps, low-cost sensors, games, and gamification) have been developed to facilitate interaction and communication between citizens and scientist and to expand the scale and scope of project and protocol design, data collection, information delivery, data processing, and visualization [7,8,9]. It is essential that citizen science platforms leverage the complementary strengths of humans and machines to take full advantage of the onslaught of data being experienced across the disciplines [10].

With the aim to deeper understand complexity of relationships at different levels of human-computer interaction in Collective Intelligence ecosystem, conceptual model was developed on the basis of theoretical insights. The framework presented in Figure 1 below provides a holistic view into the Citizen Science Hub as co-creative collective intelligence ecosystem.

Fig. 1. Citizen Science Hub as a Collective Intelligence Ecosystem

In the context of this research project, Collective Intelligence ecosystem refers to a system in which actors work together to achieve a mutual benefit – public value. The proposed model has three dimensions – actors, content and processes distributed on three levels – Micro, Meso and Macro between economic and social actors within the networks. **The actors' dimension** refers to the QH stakeholders participating in the CI ecosystem, their roles and resources. Hardy et al. [11] suggest that “although collaboration has the potential to produce powerful results, not all collaborations realize this potential. Many collaborations fail to produce innovative solutions or balance stakeholder concerns, and some even fail to generate any collective action whatsoever”. Hence, the understanding of the actors involved in ICT-enabled co-creation and the roles they can perceive is crucial [12; 13; 14; 15; 16; 17]. The concept of roles allows getting insights on the ways actors collaborate in service systems [18]. Each actor is a potential source of resources for other actors within the ecosystem. Interactions happen through creation, sharing, obtainment, and integration of the resources. Certain social

roles enable co-creation, but there are limited research on such roles and how they function together [19]. Åkesson [20] argues that heterogeneity of actors and resources involved in the ecosystems leads to productivity. Despite the diversity of actors involved in any ecosystem, it is possible to identify different types of actors, segment them and understand the nature of their relationships within a defined context. Figure 2 below shows the five types of actors identified in the research literature and types of roles they can perceive on different levels of the ecosystem.

The role of a user refers to the actors using the platform and receiving ICT-enabled service. The role of the contributor is closely related to the role of the user. However, it is more interactive and refers to more interactive collaboration efforts by means of suggesting ideas, voting, reporting issues, communicating with other contributors and other ways of creating content beneficial for the active processes of the platform. The role of the partner is to share operant resources with platform initiators and managers. The role refers to mutually beneficial relationships which are developed without losing autonomy of individual actors. Sponsors provide financial resources for enabling platform activities. The sponsoring can happen in a number of ways through governmental, business funding or citizens backing up the platforms they find important. The roles identified here can be filled by any of the actor groups identified. Meaning that the businesses can be initiators, users, contributors, initiators, partners, and sponsors of the platforms. The same applies to the citizens and other actor groups.

Fig. 2. Types of Actors and Roles in the Co-Creative Ecosystem

The **processes' dimension** includes deliberations on the patterns of design, management and collaboration in co-creating public value through human-computer interaction. Economic and social entities involved in the ecosystems have competencies expressed through the delivery of services, management of relationships with others and sharing of information through ICT tools. These attributes ensure the structural integrity of the ecosystem [21; 22; 23]. The **content dimension** includes deliberations on the goals and objectives of the actors involved. Knowing why individuals and organizations build platforms, and why citizens participate in them, can guide the organizations and civic leaders in fostering ICT-enabled platforms. **Value propositions** are used in integrated systems to connect mutually interested actors. Following the logic of Service Science, the actors able to develop the most compelling value propositions will perform the best. Lusch & Webster [24] stress the importance of constant revision of value propositions in response to changing needs of customers, suppliers and other stakeholders. CS Hubs accurately represent the ICT-enabled co-creation of public value because of the involvement of various groups of society, the employment of Web 2.0 and Web 3.0 tools and their social orientation. Due to their small scale, the components and networks of Citizen Science Hubs are more evident and more open to analysis than the more complex national systems of ICT-enabled governmental services. Hence, the services offered by the Citizen Science Hubs are only inputs in to public value creating activities in the context of civic society. The Micro level refers to the direct service-for-service exchange, i.e., end-users of the platforms. The Meso level refers to the indirect service-for-service exchange with the external stakeholders i.e. partners or competitors. The Macro level refers to the complex relationships between different systems with diverse interests co-creating public value. No one stakeholder has all the resources needed to reach their goals, and each actor is a potential source of resources for other actors within the ecosystem. Interactions happen through the digital enhanced creation, sharing, obtainment, and integration of the resources. By distributing value propositions through three levels, the framework allows to understand the value of ICT-enabled co-creation for people, organizations and society. Collective intelligence emerges in the ecosystem when a number of entities work collectively to create mutual benefits by granting access to one another's resources including people, technologies, organizations and information.

2 Validation of the Collective Intelligence Ecosystem framework

Collective Intelligence (CI) ecosystem framework was expert-validated and calibrated through a dedicated digital workshop with field experts. In particular, the workshop's purpose was to expert validate the framework by examining its dimensions and collaborations, and reflecting on its aspects and providing suggestions to its practical application by establishing Citizen Science Hubs. An information document describing the core structure of the framework and the workshop agenda were sent in advance of the workshop to the participants. The research was initiated as part of the implementation of the H2020 project INCENTIVE ("Establishing Citizen Science Hubs in European Research Performing and Funding Organisations to drive institutional change and

ground Responsible Research and Innovation in society”). The workshops was organized by Vilnius Gediminas Technical University, took place on 20 of May 2022 on MS Teams and lasted for 2 hours. During the workshop 12 experts were asked to provide their feedback and make suggestions for improving the CI ecosystem framework for adapting it for Citizen Science Hubs. The experts were identified through the author lists of European Commission H2020 public deliverables and publications regarding RRI and citizen science-related projects. The workshop with the experts provided information on *idyllic* co-creation of public value i.e. the experts discussed the potential and desired roles of governments, citizens and other actors in the ecosystem.

During the expert validation workshop six groups of actors – governmental entities, citizens, private organizations, NGOs, media, specialists – were confirmed and three more generalized actor groups – associations, public organizations and international organizations suggested to include. The discussion released, that for society to evolve for being more open and engaged, not all citizens and organizations have to be active – but there is need for intermediaries, civic leaders, active citizens who could translate the importance of active citizenship, transparency, translate the data and make it easier for citizens and governments to cooperate. The role of intermediary mostly refers to the individual actors, mostly specialists with the skills and knowledge in the fields of IT, open data, and governmental processes. Intermediaries translate the complex public sector information and processes to the other groups in the system and allow connections to happen easier. Intermediaries serve as the actor connecting the micro, meso and macro levels. In sequence, all experts’ comments were considered and incorporated into the final design of the CI ecosystem framework.

3 Conclusions and insights for future research

The long term vision of CI systems is “to fuse the knowledge, experience and expertise residing in the minds of individuals, in order to elevate, through machine facilitation, the optimal information and decisions that will lead to the benefit of the whole community” [25]. As systems become more complex and include more connections between humans and machines, the characteristics of those systems become important in determining the performance and successful development of the collaborations in the system. The challenging task for the researchers is to correlate different factors and to find realizable possibilities for the system performance in these causal relationships.

Collective Intelligence development field requires deeper research from academic and practical point of view. It would be important not only to identify the assumptions affecting development of ecosystem, but also to predict possible evolution scenarios and to define risk areas. Scientific viewpoint and analysis of the influence of social technologies on formation of Collective Intelligence raises many questions. Citizen science platforms and other networks face practical problems pertaining to the existence of a wide variety of technological tools and solutions; however, these pre-conditions do not encourage growth of Collective Intelligence since people do not collaborate, they express their opinion but do not structure it, do not assume obligations to implement decisions, etc.

From the scientific perspective, it is not the analysis of the phenomenon of Collective Intelligence in itself that is important. Future research should focus on the identification of the pre-conditions for the formation of collective intelligence, formulation of holistic conceptions and collection of empirical data. Deeper understanding of Collective Intelligence ecosystem is necessary to support Citizen Science communities to deliver intended intellectual outcomes and to provide a possibility for practitioners to integrate or create new tools and IT based solutions oriented towards societal social values.

Funding: This research was funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No. 101005330 (INCENTIVE).

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